

ArcGIS Pro Version 3.1.3 Workflow

Multispectral SIFs

- Band 1 (Blue)
 - Planetscope Scene Band 1
- Band 2 (Green)
 - Planetscope Scene Band 2
- Band 3 (Red)
 - Planetscope Scene Band 3
- Band 4 (NIR)
 - Planetscope Scene Band 4
- CIG
 - Analysis Tab → Raster → Raster Functions → Math → Band Arithmetic
 - Parameters - Raster: PlanetScope Scene, Method: CIG, Band Indexes: 4 2
- EVI
 - Analysis Tab → Raster → Raster Functions → Math → Band Arithmetic
 - Parameters - Raster: PlanetScope Scene, Method: EVI, Band Indexes: 4 3 1
- GNDVI
 - Analysis Tab → Raster → Raster Functions → Math → Band Arithmetic
 - Parameters - Raster: PlanetScope Scene, Method: GNDVI, Band Indexes: 4 2
- Iron Oxide Ratio
 - Analysis Tab → Raster → Raster Functions → Math → Band Arithmetic
 - Parameters - Raster: PlanetScope Scene, Method: Iron Oxide, Band Indexes: 3 1
- MSAVI2
 - Analysis Tab → Raster → Raster Functions → Math → Band Arithmetic
 - Parameters - Raster: PlanetScope Scene, Method: Modified SAVI, Band Indexes: 4 3
- MTVI2
 - Analysis Tab → Raster → Raster Functions → Math → Band Arithmetic
 - Parameters - Raster: PlanetScope Scene, Method: MTVI2, Band Indexes: 4 2 3
- NDVI
 - Analysis Tab → Raster → Raster Functions → Math → Band Arithmetic
 - Parameters - Raster: PlanetScope Scene, Method: NDVI, Band Indexes: 4 3
- NDWI
 - Analysis Tab → Raster → Raster Functions → Math → Band Arithmetic
 - Parameters - Raster: PlanetScope Scene, Method: NDWI, Band Indexes: 4 2
- SR
 - Analysis Tab → Raster → Raster Functions → Math → Band Arithmetic
 - Parameters - Raster: PlanetScope Scene, Method: SR, Band Indexes: 4 3
- VARI
 - Analysis Tab → Raster → Raster Functions → Math → Band Arithmetic
 - Parameters - Raster: PlanetScope Scene, Method: VARI, Band Indexes: 3 2 1

Elevation SIFs

- Elevation
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Data Management Tools → Project Raster
 - Parameters - Input Raster: GLO-30 CopDEM, Output Coordinate System: WGS_1984_UTM_Zone_35S, Resampling Technique: Cubic convolution, Output Cell Size X: 10, Output Cell Size Y: 10
- Slope
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Spatial Analyst Tools → Surface Parameters
 - Parameters - Input surface Raster: Elevation Raster, Parameter type: Slope, Local Surface Type: Quadratic, Neighborhood distance: 10 Meters, Z unit: Meter, Slope Measurement: Degree
 - Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
- Aspect
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Spatial Analyst Tools → Surface Parameters
 - Parameters - Input surface Raster: Elevation Raster, Parameter type: Aspect, Local Surface Type: Quadratic, Neighborhood distance: 10 Meters, Z unit: Meter, Project geodesic azimuths
 - Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
- Mean Curvature
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Spatial Analyst Tools → Surface Parameters
 - Parameters - Input surface Raster: Elevation Raster, Parameter type: Mean curvature, Local Surface Type: Quadratic, Neighborhood distance: 10 Meters, Z unit: Meter
 - Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
- Casorati Curvature
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Spatial Analyst Tools → Surface Parameters
 - Parameters - Input surface Raster: Elevation Raster, Parameter type: Casorati curvature, Local Surface Type: Quadratic, Neighborhood distance: 10 Meters, Z unit: Meter
 - Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
- Gaussian Curvature
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Spatial Analyst Tools → Surface Parameters
 - Parameters - Input surface Raster: Elevation Raster, Parameter type: Gaussian curvature, Local Surface Type: Quadratic, Neighborhood distance: 10 Meters, Z unit: Meter
 - Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster

- Profile Curvature
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Spatial Analyst Tools → Surface Parameters
 - Parameters - Input surface Raster: Elevation Raster, Parameter type: Profile (normal slope line) curvature, Local Surface Type: Quadratic, Neighborhood distance: 10 Meters, Z unit: Meter
 - Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
- Tangential Curvature
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Spatial Analyst Tools → Surface Parameters
 - Parameters - Input surface Raster: Elevation Raster, Parameter type: Tangential (normal contour) curvature, Local Surface Type: Quadratic, Neighborhood distance: 10 Meters, Z unit: Meter
 - Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
- TRI
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → archydropro (downloaded package) → Terrain Ruggedness Index
 - Parameters - Input Terrain Raster: Elevation Raster
- VRM
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → archydropro (downloaded package) → Terrain Ruggedness Index
 - Parameters - Input Elevation Raster: Elevation Raster, Neighborhood distance: 100 Meters, Window Size: 3
- VRM7
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → archydropro (downloaded package) → Terrain Ruggedness Index
 - Parameters - Input Elevation Raster: Elevation Raster, Neighborhood distance: 100 Meters, Window Size: 7
- Distance to Drainage Paths: large and small, no elevation
 - Fill DEM
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Spatial Analyst Tools → Fill
 - Parameters - Input surface raster: Elevation Raster
 - Environments - Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
 - Flow Direction Raster
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Spatial Analyst Tools → Flow Direction
 - Parameters - Input surface raster: Fill DEM, Flow direction type: D8
 - Environments - Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
 - Flow Accumulation Raster
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Spatial Analyst Tools → Flow Accumulation
 - Input flow direction raster: Flow Direction Raster, Output data type: Float, Input flow direction type: D8

- Environments - Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
 - Reclassified Raster, Flow Accumulation ≥ 500
 - Analysis Tab \rightarrow Geoprocessing \rightarrow Tools \rightarrow Spatial Analyst Tools \rightarrow Reclassify
 - Input raster: Flow Accumulation Raster, Reclass field: Value

Start	End	New
0	500	NODATA
500	3.65659e+06	1
NODATA	NODATA	NODATA
 - Environments - Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
 - Stream Flow 500 Polylines
 - Analysis Tab \rightarrow Geoprocessing \rightarrow Tools \rightarrow Conversion Tools \rightarrow Raster to Polyline
 - Parameters - Input raster: Reclassified Raster flow accumulation ≥ 500 , Field: Value, Background value: Zero, Minimum dangle length: 0, Simplify polylines
 - Final Raster
 - Analysis Tab \rightarrow Geoprocessing \rightarrow Tools \rightarrow Spatial Analyst Tools \rightarrow Distance Accumulation
 - Parameters - Input raster or feature source data: Stream Flow 500 polylines, Distance Method: Planar
 - Environments - Mask: Cradle Envelope, Snap Raster: Elevation Raster, Cell Size: 1
 - Distance to Drainage Paths: large and small, with elevation
 - Final Raster
 - Analysis Tab \rightarrow Geoprocessing \rightarrow Tools \rightarrow Spatial Analyst Tools \rightarrow Distance Accumulation
 - Parameters - Input raster or feature source data: Stream Flow 500 polylines, Input surface raster: Elevation Raster, Distance Method: Planar
 - Environments - Mask: Cradle Envelope, Snap Raster: Elevation Raster, Cell Size: 1
 - Distance to Drainage Paths: large streams, no elevation
 - Reclassified Raster, Flow Accumulation ≥ 2000
 - Analysis Tab \rightarrow Geoprocessing \rightarrow Tools \rightarrow Spatial Analyst Tools \rightarrow Reclassify
 - Input raster: Flow Accumulation Raster, Reclass field: Value

Start	End	New
0	2000	NODATA
2000	3.65659e+06	1
NODATA	NODATA	NODATA
 - Environments - Snap Raster: Elevation Raster

- Stream Flow 2000 Polylines
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Conversion Tools → Raster to Polyline
 - Parameters - Input raster: Reclassified Raster flow accumulation ≥ 2000 , Field: Value, Background value: Zero, Minimum dangle length: 0, Simplify polylines
- Final Raster
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Spatial Analyst Tools → Distance Accumulation
 - Parameters - Input raster or feature source data: Stream Flow 2000 polylines, Distance Method: Planar
 - Environments - Mask: Cradle Envelope, Snap Raster: Elevation Raster, Cell Size: 1
- Distance to Drainage Paths: large streams, with elevation
 - Final Raster
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Spatial Analyst Tools → Distance Accumulation
 - Parameters - Input raster or feature source data: Stream Flow 2000 polylines, Input surface raster: Elevation Raster, Distance Method: Planar
 - Environments - Mask: Cradle Envelope, Snap Raster: Elevation Raster, Cell Size: 1

Geology SIFs

- 1:250,000 Geological Polygons
 - Clipped Rustenberg 2526 Geological Polygons
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Analysis Tools → Pairwise Clip
 - Parameters - Input Features: 1:250,000 Rustenberg 2526 (1981) Geological Polygons, Clip Features: Cradle Envelope
 - Clipped West Rand 2626 Geological Polygons
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Analysis Tools → Pairwise Clip
 - Parameters - Input Features: 1:250,000 West Rand 2626 (1986) Geological Polygons, Clip Features: Cradle Envelope
 - Merged Polygons
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Data Management Tools → Merge
 - Parameters - Input Datasets: Clipped Rustenberg 2526 Geological Polygons, Clipped West Rand 2626 Geological Polygons
 - Cradle Geological Polygons
 - Edit Tab → Tools → Merge

- Manually merged individual polygons in the Merged Polygons feature with identical attributes
- Reprojected Cradle Geological Polygons
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Data Management Tools → Project
 - Parameters - Input Dataset or Feature Class: Cradle Geological Polygons, Output Coordinate System: WGS_1984_UTM_Zone_35S
- Final Feature Class
 - Reprojected Cradle Geological Polygons → Attribute Table → Add Field
 - Manually added 17 Fields: SuperGroup_Transvaal, Group_Chuniespoort, Group_Pretoria, Formation_Eccles, Formation_Lyttelton, Formation_MonteChristo, Formation_Oaktree, Formation_Rooihogte, Formation_TimeballHill, KarooDolerite, Chert_presence, Diamictite_presence, Dolomite_presence, Limestone_presence, Mudrock_presence, Quartzite_presence, Shale_presence
 - Based on information in the original LITHSTRAT, PARENT1, PARENT2, PARENT3, DESCRIPTIO attribute table fields, entered data into new fields denoting individual polygons' placement in the different geological categories, with "0" representing the polygon's absence in the supergroup/group/formation/underlying geology and "1" representing its presence
- 1: 250,000 Fault Polylines
 - Clipped Rustenberg 2526 Tectonic Lines
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Analysis Tools → Pairwise Clip
 - Parameters - Input Features: 1:250,000 Rustenberg 2526 (1981) Tectonic Lines, Clip Features: Cradle Envelope
 - Clipped West Rand 2626 Tectonic Lines
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Analysis Tools → Pairwise Clip
 - Parameters - Input Features: 1:250,000 West Rand 2626 (1986) Tectonic Lines, Clip Features: Cradle Envelope
 - Merged Tectonic Lines
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Data Management Tools → Merge
 - Parameters - Input Datasets: Clipped Rustenberg 2526 Tectonic Lines, Clipped West Rand 2626 Tectonic Lines
 - Select Fault Lines
 - Map Tab → Selection → Select By Attributes
 - Input Rows: Merged Tectonic Lines Features, Selection Type: New Selection
 - *Where* LNTYPE is equal to 10
 - Extracted Fault Lines

- Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Data Management Tools → Feature to Line
 - Input Features: Merged Tectonic Lines Features (selected fault lines)
- Cradle Fault Lines
 - Edit Tab → Tools → Merge
 - Manually merged individual polylines in the Extracted Fault Lines feature with identical attributes
- Final Feature Class
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Data Management Tools → Project
 - Parameters - Input Dataset or Feature Class: Cradle Fault Lines, Output Coordinate System: WGS_1984_UTM_Zone_35S
- 1: 250,000 Dike Polylines
 - Clipped Rustenberg 2526 Geological Lines
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Analysis Tools → Pairwise Clip
 - Parameters - Input Features: 1:250,000 Rustenberg 2526 (1981) Geological Lines, Clip Features: Cradle Envelope
 - Clipped West Rand 2626 Geological Lines
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Analysis Tools → Pairwise Clip
 - Parameters - Input Features: 1:250,000 West Rand 2626 (1986) Geological Lines, Clip Features: Cradle Envelope
 - Merged Geological Lines
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Data Management Tools → Merge
 - Parameters - Input Datasets: Clipped Rustenberg 2526 Geological Lines, Clipped West Rand 2626 Geological Lines
 - Cradle Dike Lines
 - Edit Tab → Tools → Merge
 - Manually merged individual polylines in the Extracted Fault Lines feature with identical attributes
 - Final Feature Class
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Data Management Tools → Project
 - Parameters - Input Dataset or Feature Class: Cradle Dike Lines, Output Coordinate System: WGS_1984_UTM_Zone_35S
- Transvaal Supergroup
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Conversion Tools → Polygon to Raster
 - Parameters - Input Features: 1:250,000 Geological Polygons, Value field: SuperGroup_Transvaal, Cell assignment type: Cell center, Priority field: NONE, Cellsize: 10

- Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
- Chuniespoort Group
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Conversion Tools → Polygon to Raster
 - Parameters - Input Features: 1:250,000 Geological Polygons, Value field: Group_Chuniespoort, Cell assignment type: Cell center, Priority field: NONE, Cellsize: 10
 - Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
- Pretoria Group
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Conversion Tools → Polygon to Raster
 - Parameters - Input Features: 1:250,000 Geological Polygons, Value field: Group_Pretoria, Cell assignment type: Cell center, Priority field: NONE, Cellsize: 10
 - Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
- Eccles Formation
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Conversion Tools → Polygon to Raster
 - Parameters - Input Features: 1:250,000 Geological Polygons, Value field: Formation_Eccles, Cell assignment type: Cell center, Priority field: NONE, Cellsize: 10
 - Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
- Lyttelton Formation
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Conversion Tools → Polygon to Raster
 - Parameters - Input Features: 1:250,000 Geological Polygons, Value field: Formation_Lyttelton, Cell assignment type: Cell center, Priority field: NONE, Cellsize: 10
 - Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
- Monte Christo Formation
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Conversion Tools → Polygon to Raster
 - Parameters - Input Features: 1:250,000 Geological Polygons, Value field: Formation_MonteChristo, Cell assignment type: Cell center, Priority field: NONE, Cellsize: 10
 - Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
- Oaktree Formation
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Conversion Tools → Polygon to Raster
 - Parameters - Input Features: 1:250,000 Geological Polygons, Value field: Formation_Oaktree, Cell assignment type: Cell center, Priority field: NONE, Cellsize: 10
 - Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster

- Rooihoogte Formation
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Conversion Tools → Polygon to Raster
 - Parameters - Input Features: 1:250,000 Geological Polygons, Value field: Formation_Rooihoogte, Cell assignment type: Cell center, Priority field: NONE, Cellsize: 10
 - Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
- Timeball Hill Formation
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Conversion Tools → Polygon to Raster
 - Parameters - Input Features: 1:250,000 Geological Polygons, Value field: Formation_TimeballHill, Cell assignment type: Cell center, Priority field: NONE, Cellsize: 10
 - Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
- Karoo Dolerite
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Conversion Tools → Polygon to Raster
 - Parameters - Input Features: 1:250,000 Geological Polygons, Value field: KarooDolerite, Cell assignment type: Cell center, Priority field: NONE, Cellsize: 10
 - Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
- Chert presence
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Conversion Tools → Polygon to Raster
 - Parameters - Input Features: 1:250,000 Geological Polygons, Value field: Chert_presence, Cell assignment type: Cell center, Priority field: NONE, Cellsize: 10
 - Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
- Diamictite presence
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Conversion Tools → Polygon to Raster
 - Parameters - Input Features: 1:250,000 Geological Polygons, Value field: Diamictite_presence, Cell assignment type: Cell center, Priority field: NONE, Cellsize: 10
 - Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
- Dolomite presence
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Conversion Tools → Polygon to Raster
 - Parameters - Input Features: 1:250,000 Geological Polygons, Value field: Dolomite_presence, Cell assignment type: Cell center, Priority field: NONE, Cellsize: 10
 - Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster

- Limestone presence
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Conversion Tools → Polygon to Raster
 - Parameters - Input Features: 1:250,000 Geological Polygons, Value field: Limestone_presence, Cell assignment type: Cell center, Priority field: NONE, Cellsize: 10
 - Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
- Mudrock presence
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Conversion Tools → Polygon to Raster
 - Parameters - Input Features: 1:250,000 Geological Polygons, Value field: Mudrock_presence, Cell assignment type: Cell center, Priority field: NONE, Cellsize: 10
 - Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
- Quartzite presence
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Conversion Tools → Polygon to Raster
 - Parameters - Input Features: 1:250,000 Geological Polygons, Value field: Quartzite_presence, Cell assignment type: Cell center, Priority field: NONE, Cellsize: 10
 - Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
- Shale presence
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Conversion Tools → Polygon to Raster
 - Parameters - Input Features: 1:250,000 Geological Polygons, Value field: Shale_presence, Cell assignment type: Cell center, Priority field: NONE, Cellsize: 10
 - Environments – Snap Raster: Elevation Raster
- Distance to Faults
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Spatial Analyst Tools → Distance Accumulation
 - Parameters - Input raster or feature source data: 1: 250,000 Fault polylines, Distance Method: Planar
 - Environments - Mask: Cradle Envelope, Snap Raster: Elevation Raster, Cell Size: 1
- Distance to Dikes
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Spatial Analyst Tools → Distance Accumulation
 - Parameters - Input raster or feature source data: 1: 250,000 Dike polylines, Distance Method: Planar
 - Environments - Mask: Cradle Envelope, Snap Raster: Elevation Raster, Cell Size: 1

Locality Training Dataset with Extracted SIF Values

- Cave/Sinkhole Training Dataset
 - Pixel Points (representing 10x10 pixel centers as points using 10m DEM)
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Conversion Tools → Raster to Point
 - Parameters - Input Raster: DEM, Field: Value
 - Positive Training Points
 - Map Tab → Selection → Select By Polygon
 - Manually selected relevant training points (n=1080), holding Shift key to add to current selection
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Data Management Tools → Copy Features
 - Parameters - Input Features: Pixel Points, Toggle On: Use the selected records
 - Positive Points with Extracted SIF Values
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Spatial Analyst Tools → Extract Multi Values to Points
 - Parameters - Input Point Features: Positive Points, Input rasters: all 48 SIF rasters
 - Final Positive Points
 - Cradle Envelope Cave Points with Extracted SIF Values → Attribute Table → Add Field
 - Manually added two Fields: Target and Cluster
 - Using Calculate Field, set Target Field to 1
 - Individual Clusters were manually selected and their Cluster Field Value changed. Fossil Sites assigned to Cluster numbers 1-15, and Map Interpreted sites assigned 16-75
- Random Background Point Training Dataset
 - Random Points
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Data Management Tools → Create Random Points
 - Parameters - Constraining Feature Class: Cradle Boundary, Number of Points: 1085 (slightly over n), Minimum Allowed Distance: 11 Meters
 - Environments – Output Coordinate System: WGS_1984_UTM_Zone_35S
 - Background Points
 - Map Tab → Selection → Select By Location
 - Input Features: Random Points, Relationship: Within a distance, Selecting Features: Cave Training Dataset, Search Distance: 50 Meters, Selection Type: New Selection
 - Random Points within 50 m of cave points (5 total) manually deleted

- Background Points with Extracted SIF Values
 - Analysis Tab → Geoprocessing → Tools → Spatial Analyst Tools → Extract Multi Values to Points
 - Parameters - Input Point Features: Background Points, Input rasters: all 48 SIF rasters
- Final Background Points
 - Background Points with Extracted SIF Values → Attribute Table → Add Field
 - Manually added two Fields: Target and Cluster
 - Using Calculate Field, set Target Field to 0
 - Cluster Field values maintained as NaN (no clustering in the background dataset)
- Final Tables for Machine Learning in Python
 - Final Positive Points → Data → Export Table (Input Table: Final Positive Points, export as .csv)
 - Final Background Points → Data → Export Table (Input Table: Final Background Points, export as .csv)
 - Table merging and fold creation conducted in Python (see Furtner_etal_2026_JArchaeolMethodTheory_PythonCode.py)